

Philosophical Perspectives to Teaching Moral Philosophy in Nigerian Schools

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Abstract

This paper discusses the views of philosophers and other contemporary scholars on moral philosophy and their contributions to moral education. Also, in this paper the researchers intend to review the conception of moral education based on schools of philosophical thought which include idealism, realism, pragmatism and existentialism as each of these schools of philosophy has its own perception of what moral education stands for and through their ethical views each of these schools suggests one or more approach which might quite differ from the perception of the other schools of philosophy. In each of these schools of philosophical thought the researcher decides to take the view of one or more exponent of each school of philosophy and carefully study their views on epistemology, metaphysics and ethics so as to exposé how they viewed moral education in general and moral education in particular with the hope that the approach suggested for teaching moral education would be brought out. This will in turn throw light on which approach out of the approaches suggested by philosophers of different schools of philosophies will be suitable for teaching moral education in Nigerian schools.

Keywords: Moral philosophy perspectives, School of philosophical thoughts, Moral education

Introduction

This paper discusses the views of philosophers and other contemporary scholars on moral education. Also, in this paper the researchers intend to review the conception of moral education based on schools of philosophical thought which include idealism, realism, pragmatism and existentialism as each of these schools of philosophy has its own perception of what moral education stands for and through their ethical views each of these schools suggests one or more approach which might quite

differ from the perception of the other schools of philosophy.

In each of these schools of philosophical thought the researchers decide to take the view of one or more exponent of each school of philosophy and carefully study their views on epistemology, metaphysics and ethics so as to exposé how they viewed moral education in general and moral education in particular with the hope that the approach suggested for teaching moral education would be brought out. This will in turn throw light on which approach out of the approaches suggested by philosophers

of different schools of philosophies will be suitable for teaching moral education in Nigerian schools.

The researchers decide to analyse the conception of philosophers of these schools of philosophy because of the relevance of the ideologies of each school to the Nigerian education system and also because of the presence of some of the ideologies of these schools of philosophy in Nigerian educational practice. These schools of philosophical thoughts include; Idealism, Realism, Pragmatism, Existentialism.

Idealist Conception of Moral Education

According to Akinpelu (1998) Idealism is perhaps the oldest philosophy in western culture dating back to Plato in ancient Greece. Of course, philosophy and philosophers existed before Plato, but Plato developed one of the most historically influenced philosophies of education we have. Idealists hold the reality behind every existence to be spiritual in nature as its metaphysical view. Man, to idealist is a physical being with the most essential component of soul as the reality behind the physical body. Bagudo (2002) gives a detail explanation of the Plato's attempt in his book "*the Republic*", to draw a line of demarcation between the world of ideas and the material world. Mind, spirit and idea are central in idealistic conception of reality. Physical world to idealist is just an imperfect reflection of the real world which Plato called "world of forms". Plato's allegory of the cave presents a clear explanation of the darkness of ignorance to humans and the light of knowledge which Plato regarded as virtue.

It is this metaphysical view of idealist that dictates the nature of their education. Man being made up of spiritual and physical component with supremacy of the spiritual self over physical component, needs to be given a type of education worthy of

developing his spiritual and mental capacities. Education to idealist is meant for self realization, self actualization, spiritual, mental and physical development of man in this world in preparation for life in the world of forms (Omogbe, 2000). Therefore, idealist view on education stresses the intellectual development of man through acquisition of a number of virtues the most important of which is justice as Socrates claimed.

Plato, in Mango (2011) when buttressing the statement made by his master Socrates, "knowledge is virtue and ignorance is vice" To him, all evil doers are suffering from ignorance for no man can do what he knows can harm him and neither can he be said to know the negative implication of his action on others and still dwell into its performance. The aim of education of a child to an idealist should be centered on the intellectual development, constant search for truth and character development for the overall development of the society¹. Idealists do not only concern themselves with the teaching of literature, gymnastics, music and provision of quantitative knowledge, but development of reflective and critical thinking in a child, character and moral development and provision of morally sounded people whose rational thinking directs their worthy actions (Yabo, 2000).

Morality and character development are two cardinal issues that dominate idealists' system of education. It is absolutely clear that idealist system of education aims at spiritual development of man, detaching man from worldly illusions to the formation of good character in man as directed towards attainment of optimal moral disposition by man in relation to his environment and other members of his society. To Plato, knowledge is not created by human but they rather discover it. He conjectured that the human soul once had true knowledge but lost it by

being placed in a material body which distorted and corrupted that knowledge (Enoh, 2000). This states that idealist hold education as a process of recollection of the forgotten knowledge of human being (*educere*). Plato believed in the possession of innate idea in man to help to bring out which an education system should be geared to. But this has created a wide gap which this paper attempts to fill. As explained above education to idealist rests solemnly on spiritual, mental and character development which are directly concerned with morality of human being. Education as a process of acquiring the worthwhile is only realized by manifestation of worthy actions to qualify individual to be called educated. Does human being attain moral development haphazardly? How does the teaching of moral values going to be approached?

Plato suggested that state must take an active role in educational concerns and offer a curriculum that leads intelligent students from concrete data towards abstract thinking (Ebcarr Dictionary) This portrays the idealist conception of education as a state affair, an instrument for societal change and progress for the better. Moral disposition of a person entails respect for one's self, respect for human dignity and obedience to constituted authorities and societal rules and regulations. State is interested in the overall societal development with individuals as machineries to the attainment of such development. Therefore, Nigeria's quest for the development of individual into a sound and effective citizen and their full integration into the community remains only a mere wish unless there is a provision, for the individual, of the right type of values inculcated into their minds through a well organized and a specifically stated subject-content in the Nigerian school curriculum to be taught by teachers under a well suitable approach. The belief of the idealist in the reason as a source

of true knowledge has also influence their educational ideas. To idealists, true knowledge can not be acquired only by the sense perception, it is the reasoning faculty of individual learner that is capable of giving avenues to the ultimate truth which the whole idealism doctrine rest upon (Mango, 2011)

Saint Augustine, a Neo-Platonist, agreed with Plato that the highest aim of education is the search for the truth, but he believed even more strongly than Plato that truth has over whelming spiritual implications. According to Augustine, the search for truth is a search for God, and a true education leads one to God because, to him, God is the pure idea. God can be reached only through contemplation of ideas. Therefore, a true education is concerned with ideas rather than matter (Bagudo, 2011). With regard to this, Augustine made it clear that religious principles are the gateway to the full integration of individual learner into a virtuous life. He gives a religious approach to educating a man. Since he considered God as the true idea, education should aim at fostering man's vision of God and obeying his commandments.

None of the revealed religions teach immorality, says Bagudo (2002) and thus, from this, it can be deduced that idealist' educational views revolve around spiritual and mental development, character and moral development of man. Religion can be used to teach morality in Nigerian schools. In Nigerian school system, is religious approach being used to teach moral education? It may be doubtful if there is any claim from an authoritative source to give testimony to that and even if there is one, there is no certainty that it may not be ascribing to conversion to one particular religion rather than using religious doctrines of commitment and devotion for societal growth, cooperation and harmony.

Idealists suggested, from the aforementioned, two approaches to moral education i.e. religious approach and cognitive development approach. One of the strengths of idealism according to Adherants (2003) is the promotion of high cognitive level of education. It is clear and obvious that in order that an individual be morally sound, capable of making rational choice and optimal level of moral judgment, he has to be cognitively developed. According to cognitive development theory, moral development in man passes through hierarchical stages which simultaneously go with ages. Character development entails inner moral disposition and moral outlook in a learner. Idealists also are of the opinion that knowledge is acquired through reason which is an avenue for deep reflection on matters of abstraction and ability to thinking positively so as to develop such potentials inherent in human nature.

The doctrine of Reminiscence was explained by Plato, as buttressed by Ozmon (2006) under which the soul recollects the true knowledge it lost in the process of its imprisonment in the body. Plato upholds that morality in individual originated from individual reasoning capacity and the most cherishable value is the 'good will' which helps to direct personal choice, rational and moral judgement as well as attainment of conscience to a greater height. Plato is of the view that the process of recollection of the innate potentialities in man is possible through dialogue, Socrates or dialectic method. This indicates the adoption of questioning method in teaching moral values to individual learner. Dialectic method is all about asking critical question that triggers thought in individual learner on a concept, issue or a problem in question. It is a method of asking question in order to gain a particular knowledge by the process of deductive reasoning, that is beginning with particular

cases and ending up in the universal knowledge as a conclusion.ⁱⁱ It was discussed earlier that education to idealist is all about attaining some moral virtues by an individual both for his betterment and that of his society. It is indisputable that dialectic method is chosen by Socrates to teach such values as justice, generosity, kindness, truthfulness e.t.c. by opening the misconception in the opponent's opinion. This is the first stage which is called 'opinion stage'. The second stage is called 'synthetic stage' in which the opponent is brought to see the misconception ingrained in his opinion. The last stage is 'stage of destruction' in which the opponent is made to drop his opinion to the opinion proved to be sounder than the opponent's perception (Mango, 2011)

In this process, Socrates stands only as clarifier of the conception and perception of his student, a glance at which portrays the use of what is currently referred to as values clarification approach. In this approach a teacher stands as a clarifier of values that his/her student presents in the course of their discussion and not imposing his ideas on them (Mango 2011) Idealist, as proved by Socrates' dialectic method holds 'values clarification' as an approach to teaching moral values to their student. Can it be said that values clarification approach to moral education is being used to teach moral education in Nigerian schools where the teachers are in contemplation of the contents to teach as moral education or is it mentioned anywhere in the National policy on education, a declaration of values clarification approach as a formally specified approach to use in teaching moral education in Nigerian schools?

In Nigerian school system claim for teaching moral education remains only a suggestion that is not adequately theorized so as to be put to practice for realization. This is because teaching activity may not be

effective without a specific approach to the subject matter. This research would therefore attempt to bridge the gap between teaching moral education in Nigerian schools and approaches postulated by idealists' philosophers such as Socrates, Plato and Augustine who advocated for approaches like religious approach, Cognitive development approach and values clarification approach. Subsequently, these approaches would be examined in order to find a suitable approach for Nigerian schools in which we don't have any specified approach.

Realist Conception of Moral Education

According to Passabiru (2000) Realism as a philosophical school of thought exists hand in hand with idealism as they both trace their origin from the fundamental western civilization of Greek. Realism is a direct opposite to idealism based on their metaphysical and epistemological views. The basic principle of realist's metaphysical view is that the reality behind every existence is the matter as opposed to idealist who holds the reality of every existence as spiritual in nature. Realist epistemological view differs from that of idealist as realist hold that knowledge is acquired through experience registered through the human senses (sense of sight, sense of hearing sense of feeding taste bud and sense of perception). Realism acknowledges and accepts unity between essential and existence the nature and existence of object which are captured by five senses and understood by the mind.

Realist general conception of education is that education should acquaint individual learner with essential skills and knowledge needed for individual survival (Ozmon 2003). They believed that knowledge is acquired independent of the mind. John lock explained that human being should cultivate a sound body and mind through education (Bagudo, 2004) Education

according to realism will be formulated as an effort to develop the potentials of every existence. They hold that the nature of reality is on the things or objects not something that escapes or is released from its owner. Therefore, it is natural that the first concern in education is what is on the learner. The followers of realism have agreement on the basic principles of educational realism which include: learning to essentially put the attention on the learners as it is, initiatives in education should emphasize education rather than children, the core of the educational process is the assimilation of the subject matter that has been determined. Education in realist' views are a systematic process that follows step by step procedures that leads to the attainment of the desired end.

Realist strongly believes in scientific method especially when it comes to learning. No knowledge can be said to be true if it cannot be proved scientifically. This has obviously pointed out that any accepted knowledge is protectable and continuous and scientific discoveries are tentative subject to periodical changes as a result of further manipulation of the scientific findings.

Realist views on moral education could be seen clearly in the ethics of the prominent realist philosopher, Aristotle. According to Aristotle all human actions are performed in order to attain some ends. That is every human action is a means to an end which is sought only as means to further end. There is however, one end which is sought for its own sake, this he says, is happiness.ⁱⁱⁱ According to Aristotle, the purpose of morality is happiness because all other actions are geared towards attainment of happiness which is end in itself i.e. it is happiness that is the standard of morality. Therefore, every one wishing to be happy must live a moral life. To Aristotle, morality is the only way to happiness. Aristotle holds that happiness is an activity of the soul in

accordance with virtue. This means that virtue is the only way to happiness.

Omoregbe (2000) mentioned two different virtues, thus: Intellectual virtues and moral virtues. Intellectual virtues could be attained through the avenues of scientific knowledge; art practical wisdom, intuitive reason, theoretical wisdom, sound deliberation; understanding and judgment were considered by Aristotle as intellectual virtues. To this end, Aristotle advocates for the inclusion of science subject in the school curriculum as well as art subjects. Teaching of science subjects, to Aristotle, widens student's intellectual ability and the spirit of making discovery free to try out things without allowing fables to limit the spirit of inquiry.

This postulation by Aristotle stresses the approach to the moral education to be cognitive development approach. This is because independent thinking and self indulged act of finding truth requires a high sense of cognitive advancement in individual learner. With reference to Nigerian school system, this paper is much concerned with approaches to moral education, it is imperative to ask 'is cognitive development approach adopted to teach moral education in Nigerian schools? No policy document can testify to that.

The other virtue is 'moral virtue' which includes Justice, Temperance, Generosity, Courage etc. Doctrine of 'Golden mean' was taught by Aristotle to explain what he means by virtue. He identifies virtue as a means between two extreme ends namely excess and defect. (Omoregbe, 2000). For example, generosity is a mean (i.e. the midway) between miserliness (an extreme) and extravagance (another extreme) Aristotle, through the doctrine of Golden mean regards moral education as a struggle to take a medium position between two extremes i.e. excess and defect which is

acquired through the persistent practice for a long period. In other words, it is a character acquired through constant practice and or experience (Passabiru, 2000) Therefore moral education to Aristotle aims at making individual learner acquire certain moral virtues which include Generosity, Temperance, Justice, Courage and Honesty through constant practice in every day affairs. Teaching individual learner to value a virtue and habitually put it to practice requires the use of effective approach which necessitates easy acquaintance of such virtue to an individual learner.

Realist emphasizes the role of intelligence as it formulates the concepts and develops general and abstract ideals. The realists of all brands aver that values are permanent and objective and say that although institution and practice vary a great deal, the fundamental values of the society should not change. The children should be taught the nature of right and wrong and what is objectively good and beautiful. As realist believed in the role of intelligence in the inculcation of fundamental values of the society into the minds of the students, it stresses the sense experience as the gateway to the attainment of moral conscience.

To this extent, realist opts strongly for the approach that leads to the intellectual development in an individual learner. In other words, realist advocated for cognitive development approach where, student should be taught to understand the cherishable values of the society and to be able to judge morally on what action is right and which is wrong. In relation to Nigerian school system, no sign of emulation was made of any approach to moral education as postulated by realism. The role of intelligence is emphasized in the area of science and technology but not as a pre condition for teaching moral education. In Nigerian schools a problem which this paper attempt

to starts addressing is by examining the approaches postulated by realist so as to find out whether or not it would be suitable for teaching moral education in Nigerian schools.

Pragmatists Conception of Moral Education

According to Akinpelu (1998), Pragmatism is a philosophical movement developed near the turn of the century in the work of several prominent American philosophers most notably Charles Sanders Peirce, William James and John Dewey. Although many contemporary analytic philosophers never studied American philosophy in graduate school, analytic philosophy has been significantly shaped by philosophers strongly influenced by that tradition, most especially W.V. Quine, Donald Davidson, Hillary Putnam and Richard Rorty. Like other philosophical movements, it developed in response to the then dominant philosophical wisdom. In pragmatism, practice is primary in philosophy. Meaningful inquiry originates in practice. Theorizing is valuable, for sure, but its value arises from practice which is informed by practices and its proper aim is to clarify, coordinate and inform practice. Pragmatist considers theorizing divorced from practice as rather useless.

Pragmatism is a philosophy of action. It is concerned with the usefulness, effect and difference that occur in something as a result of its interaction with that thing. As a philosophy of human action, it rejects metaphysics because it is mere speculation without purpose. The ultimate reality of existence for pragmatist is experience which resulted from man's interaction with his environment. And therefore, knowledge is the processing of experience and the outcome of that processing.^{iv} Pragmatic school of philosophical thought believed that

knowledge and indeed everything in the world keeps changing as opposed to idealists. In pragmatism, concern is less accorded to metaphysics and more accorded to life and human interest. It is essentially a humanistic philosophy which upholds that man is responsible for the creation of his own values in the course of activity. This is to enable an individual to think of what to do in a life situation when problem occur, it focuses on the development of creative powers and functional activities of the human mind to enable him to bring about social change for the benefit of man.^v The whole idea of education to pragmatist is on the encouragement of individual learner to grow in his experience through experience, excursion and problem solving. (Yabo, 2000)

The ethical views of pragmatist acknowledge that ethical judgment is relative without being relativistic. And it tolerates and indeed welcomes some moral differences without being irresolute. Ethical theorizing begins when we think about how we ought to live. Many people assume that means we must look for moral criteria; some list of rules or principles whereby we can distinguish good from bad and right from wrong, or a list of virtues we try to inculcate. (Passabiru, 2000)

Pragmatist views on moral education could be traced in Dewey's conception of moral education. Dewey's pragmatism did not allow him to develop a coherent theory of moral education. He suggests that moral education can be associated with virtue ethics, yet although he used conspicuously moral terms 'virtues' and 'habits' through out his writings, this did not amount to a workable theory of moral education. To Dewey, virtue amounted to the cultivation of correct habits which he deemed to be of primary concern to education. He saw all knowledge as acquired by scientific-like methods. This was one of the central theses

of pragmatism. John Childs^{vi} summarizes the pragmatic views on education, which hold that the entire program of school should be permeated by the intellectual moral attitudes inherent in the practice of experimental inquiry. They are united in the conviction that the young should be systematically nurtured in those attitudes and procedures which will dispose them in all aspect of their experience to test and ‘true up’ their ideas by whatever evidence bear on them.

To Dewey knowledge was essentially a result of scientific inquiry. The only moral knowledge one can seemingly talk about is developed through procedural inquiry with respect to moral reasoning. Since moral knowledge as any other knowledge, emerges from experience. Moral reasoning is guided by moral values or norms that prevail in a given society. While acknowledging this, Dewey simultaneously refuses to let any particular code of moral values be presented to students as mandatory. All of this is consistent with the pragmatist approach which maintains substantive flexibility by assuming that scientific method of reasoning is the most reliable (Mango, 2008)

Dewey saw virtues as certain kind of habits demonstrated in a particular circumstance. Therefore, in order for an individual learner to acquire moral virtues; he has to exercise constants practice of an action to reach to certain level of maturity to become a habit. For Dewey, the identification of a habit as virtuous has to vary. This is so because habits are indispensable in the acquisition of knowledge since knowledge is gained through intelligent inquiry and habits are necessary for the intelligent inquiry and because knowledge is gained only by the interaction between the learner and the environment. Thus, changes in the environment changes the habits and change their status as virtuous or vices as well.

Dewey identified the formulation of habits with principles for he explicitly remarked that a principle is but another name for continuity of the activity and so is habit, which is a manner of action. He rejected any possibility of a priori analytical principles referring to them as the philosophic fallacy (Passabiru, 2000) This explains that principles which are no more than habits brought to the awareness of the individual who possess them, are changing as they react to the changes in the environment. To Dewey, all habits are dynamic, propulsive and projective and they constitute self. It is dynamic because it changes with change in the physical and social environment of the person.

The view of pragmatist that man is responsible for the creation of value in the course of activity which is to enable him to think of what to do in a life situation when problem occur, and which focuses on the development of creative powers and functional activities of human mind to enable him to bring about social change for the benefit of man, it could be deduced from this point that for individual to think positively and creates his own values to bring about changes for the better, a wide range of moral conscience is needed which may be attained through a corresponding high sense of cognitive development. Thus, the idea of approach which pragmatist suggests for the teaching of moral education could be cognitive development approach. This is so because values are what keeps society functional, harmonious and peaceful and guarantees peaceful coexistence among its members. For example, the prohibition of murder and illegal assassination of human being is meant to protect the dignity of human life, thereby according highest value to human life.

Pragmatist view on the changing nature of principles which are formed by

constant practice of habits and the view that moral reasoning is guided by moral values or norms that prevail in a given society are clear signs of the adaptation of values clarification approach to teaching moral education since for man to reason morally a set of values considered most cherishable by the society has to be his guiding principles. Therefore, a teacher as an agent of the society in the moral training of the young citizens, is hold responsible for the clarification of such values society appreciates as worthy of acquisition by the teeming learners. Each of these two approaches namely: cognitive development approach and values clarification approach could be used to teach moral education in Nigerian schools so as to start the journey from this point.

Existentialist's Conception of Moral Education

Existentialism is a school of philosophical thought developed as a result of the excess of high industrialization and of the evil effects of the progress of science and technology in the developed countries.^{vii} Existentialism is described as a philosophy of existence. It concerns itself with human concrete existence, thinking, feeling and acting individual. Existentialism disregards any metaphysical or abstract speculation about the nature, essence and reality of every existence. To existentialist the reality is in what we see, hear, feel, touch and perceived on concrete human existence. As against idealist, existentialist sees it rather useless to bother with other speculative qualities of man when the world is full of chaos and problems for man to proper solution to for the advancement of his life.

Bamisaie, in Bagudo (2002) divided existentialist into two groups namely: Religion existentialist and secular and atheistic existentialist. Religious existentialist holds the view that the world is

new and informed throughout with God's subsistent essence, the importance of personal life and man bears the essence of his responsibility and capacity through his behaviours to reach the city of God. While Atheistic existentialist are of the view that man's existence precedes his essence. According to them, man is totally free and then totally responsible for himself and his actions in the world.

The nature of reality to existentialist is subjective and lies within the individual. The physical world has no inherent meaning outside of human existence. Individual choice and individual standards rather than external standards are central. Existence comes before any definition of what we are. We define ourselves in relation to that existence by the choice we make. We should not accept anyone else's predetermine philosophical system, rather we must take responsibility for deciding who we are. The focus is on freedom, the development of reliable individual, as we make meaning of our lives.

There are several different orientations within the existentialist philosophy. Soren Kierkegaard (1813-1855) Minister and Philosopher is considered to be the founder of existentialism. He has a Christian orientation. Another group of existentialists largely European, believes that we must recognize the fitness of our lives on this small and fragile planet, rather than believing in salvation through God. Our existence is no guaranteed in an after life. So, there is tension about life and certainty of death, of hope or despair. Unlike the more ouster European approaches where the universe is seen as meaningless when faces with the certainty of the end of existence, American existentialists have focuses more on human potential and the quest for personal meaning. Value clarification is an outgrowth of this movement. Following the bleak period

of World War II, the French philosopher, Jean Paul Sartre suggested that for youth, the existential movement arises when young persons realize for the first time that choice is theirs, that they are responsible for themselves. Their question becomes who am I and what should I do (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy).

Generally, the most fundamental principle of existentialism according to Akinpelu (1988) is that man is a free and self-determining individual. A man has a unique personality which is not duplicated in any other man. On the theory of knowledge, existentialists accorded less priority to rationality and scientific objectivity because, to them, rationality and scientific objectivity delays action in a given situation (Akinpelu, 1998).

Existentialist views on moral education are adequately found in the ethics of Immanuel Kant popularly known as 'Kantian ethics. To Kant^{viii} there is only one virtue that is worthy of acquisition without qualification and that is what he termed to be 'good will'. All other things generally considered as good are not unconditionally good, their goodness need to be qualified for they can either be used positively or negatively. Kant further explains good will as a will which acts for the sake of duty. He also marked the difference between acting for the sake of duty and acting according to duty. To act for the sake of duty stands for acting in accordance with the dictates of moral law while acting according to duty takes the form of acting for the sake of pursuing human or personal interest. To Kant, Principle of universalization is the yardstick for measuring the morality of an action. For us to know whether or not the action we intend to perform is morally right, consideration of the maxim of an action should be taken and principle of universalization should be applied. Maxim of an action and principle are

two distinct concepts. In this regard, while the later stands for subject principle on which a person is defacto acting, the former is an objective moral law on which every man ought to act (Akinpelu, 1998)

Moral law according to Kant is self-imposed law.^{ix} It is a man's rational will which impose on itself the moral law. Since, the imposition of moral law is determined by the level of man's rationality. Kant's views suggest an approach that would bring in man higher rational development for rationality to be influential enough to impose moral law on itself. From this, it could be asserted that an approach that may leads to the attainment of high level of rationality in man could be cognitive development approach, for it is believed that cognitive development enhances critical thinking, good moral and rational judgement of issues and enlargement of broader understanding in man. Kant^x also regards the autonomy of the will as the supreme principle of morality, good will as pointed earlier, is the worth virtue to acquire.

Bagudo (2014) explained moralization as a means through which that type of mind which chooses good aim is acquired. Thus, if the type of mind which chooses good aim is acquired through moralization, then moral education stands as a means of training human mind to acquire the worth virtue, which in Kantian ethics is considered to be 'good will'. Therefore, the development of human mind towards acquiring good will is the idea behind moral education. In this respect, an approach suitable for the teaching of moral education is asserted to be cognitive development approach as it is the gateway to a greater rational development in man.

Bamisaiye's attempt to divide existentialism into two groups i.e. religion existentialism and secular and atheistic existentialism where religion existentialists advocates for the kind of approach that would

provide man with vast knowledge that could lead him to reach the city of God, and secular and atheistic existentialist holds that man's existence proceeds his essence and man is totally free and responsible for himself and his actions stresses the use of two different approaches one for each group of existentialist philosophers (Bagudo, 2002)

A religious existentialist opts for religious approach to moral education for peaceful and better existence in man's environment. It is believed that all revealed religions teach morality and condemn immorality to a greater height. The other group known as secular and atheistic existentialists philosophers, based on their secularism advocates for secular approach to moral education which entails free religious and ethnic affiliation in the process of teaching moral education. To them secular approach to moral education is more suitable for teaching moral education.

Nigeria is a secular state where no single religion prevails over others and is multi ethnic and multi cultural in nature. Therefore, secular approach could be used if appropriately adopted, to teach moral education in Nigerian schools effectively.

Conclusion

Education is a universal concept the essence of which is seen in the ethical aspect of human life. Therefore, moral education is the standard and yardstick for measuring the worthiness of any claim to education acquired in any part of the world. Every society has its unique peculiarities in the nature, culture and way of transmitting knowledge to younger generation. Nigeria as a nation is multi-religious, multi-ethnic, multi-cultural and multi-lingual in nature and therefore needs to have common approach which could be adopted to all religions and all Nigerian cultures.

Nigerian education system adopted a unidirectional approach to teaching moral education which is 'Religious approach' as reflected in the subjects of Islamic religion knowledge and Christian religion knowledge, thereby attributing the responsibility of teaching moral education to only religious subject teachers. Many teachers in Nigerian school are in dilemma as to whether moral education exists in Nigerian school curriculum because of absence of any subject titled moral education in it or time slot allocated for teaching moral education. This is the reason why many Nigerian teachers do not consider themselves as moral instructors

Religious approach to moral education which is adopted by Nigeria has failed to adequately address the issue of moral education among Nigerian students. This is because of the rampant immoral practices witnessed among Nigerians, hence the need for its complementation, reconstruction or replacement.

Nigeria is a secular state. Therefore, Religious approach cannot be accommodated by all the Nigerian schools and the professor of other religions. Hence the need for alternating the age long religious approach with multi dimensional approach as alternative to religious approach for its flexibility and is religious-free. It only uses school subjects and other extra-curricular activities that are applicable to virtually all Nigerian ethnic groups, religious denominations, cultural group and all the Nigerian tribes.

Recommendations

1. There is an urgent need for the review of Nigerian school curriculum to match the existential realities in terms of moral decadence among Nigerians with commensurate approaches to moral education to reverse the ugly trend.

2. There should be a good and effective means for periodic assessment and evaluation of teachers' moral disposition in respect to their interaction with their students. Because some teachers' immoral attitudes and lack of good relationship between teachers and students hinders the effort to address the problem of moral education in Nigeria. This should start right from take-off stage of the appointment, where teachers on appointment would be fully assessed in their moral disposition and outlook in addition to personality assessment, vocal expression, physical fitness and mastery of subject area. All these metamorphose and manifest in the moral function of a teacher during the course of his/her interaction with the school community. It could also be in the form of giving out 'Moral Assessment Form' to students to respond to the questions aimed at providing information about the moral being of teachers in their teaching responsibility.
3. Employers of labour should reduce the priority they accord to paper qualification. Rather, they should lay much emphasis on the moral soundness of graduates from Nigerian schools as their employees. This could be encouraged through going to school, employing those that are morally sound as teachers and school administrators.

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